

Generational Social Problems in Soviet and Post-Soviet Uzbekistan

Fozila Kurbonova ✉

Student of School of Engineering named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract

Uzbekistan has faced major social problems that shaped and complicated everyday life of folk during the late 1980-1990s, a period of Soviet Union decline and new challenges occurring. Using historical accounts, archival reports and secondary studies, this research explores three pressing issues. Firstly, it explores the exploitation of children in cotton harvesting exhibiting both economic pressure and negative impact of the Soviet labour system. Secondly, this research analyses the repetitive tragic occasions of women self-demolition, which revealed the persistence of domestic violence and poor institutional support for women. Lastly, the distribution of underground gambling among men, causing economic and social instability, is highly observed. Together, the study unites these phenomena to demonstrate how structural inequalities, cultural pressures and destabilization affected Uzbek families and communities. The results show that social stress in the late Soviet period was not limited to political and economic consequences, but also manifested in terms of family, labour, and community life.

Keywords: *Social problems, child labour, women self-immolation, underground gambling, cotton harvesting, gender inequality.*

Suggested citation: Kurbonova, F. (2025). Generational Social Problems in Soviet and Post-Soviet Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(6), 81-86. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(6).09

Introduction

The last years of the Soviet Union were a harsh time for its republics, accompanied by economic decline and political crisis. Similarly, Uzbekistan struggled with socioeconomic problems that were apparent not only at the government level, but also influenced the everyday life of ordinary people. While the political side of the USSR collapse gained more attention from historians, hidden social issues began to reveal their nature, exhibiting the tension between official ideology and lived reality. Its impact is equally important for understanding that period and people at that time. Social problems, such as economic demands and cultural pressures, have caused hardships to many citizens, from the youngest children to men and women. The widespread exploitation of children aged 11-17 explored the poverty aspects and neglect of child care. Meanwhile, the acts of self-immolation among Uzbek women became more widespread, having domestic abuse and harsh lifestyles of the rural village culture as motivating factors. Furthermore, the existence of underground gambling in the USSR also occupied Uzbekistan, making men addicted to it as a chance of escape. This paper examines these three aspects more clearly to reveal how social life reflected the broader Soviet decline.

Literature Review

The various social sides of the 80s and 90s have been explored by scholars from Central Asia and other parts of the world. Some studies consider the causes, practices, and effects of child labour in Uzbekistan's cotton sector, linking it to poverty, state-controlled cotton production, and education gaps (Bilal Ahmad

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Bhat, 2011). The thesis emphasizes that government quotas, economic dependence on cotton exports, and limited employment opportunities in rural areas combine to force families to resort to child labor during harvest. Also, the public recognition that children pick cotton is due to long-standing agricultural traditions that date back to the Soviet era. In turn, cultural child-rearing norms, such as obedience and family expectation, help sustain the government's use of child forced labour in the cotton harvest as well (Kathleen Crowley, 2016). These factors, as Crowley claims, show the use of children in cotton labor not as exploitation, but as a moral contribution to family and nation. Thus, the socio-cultural challenges emphasize the role of socialization in perpetuating systemic labor practice. However, even though deterrence and poverty still persisted, international pressures have raised awareness (Patricia Jurewicz, 2014). Child labor was reduced because of the effectiveness of global efforts, such as trade sanctions and limitations, along with public commitment to combat the problem.

Elizabeth A. Campbell's 2005 dissertation examines the reasons of some women's attempt of suicide by fire in Uzbekistan. By interviewing survivors, she found that self-immolation was not driven by religion or had symbolic meanings, but mostly occurred due to domestic abuse and difficult social conditions. Her research reveals how the systematic silence about the suffering of Uzbek women reflects the reality of broad patriarchal norms rooted in both family and government structures. With recent analysis of Saodat, a women's magazine between 1989-1991, the Umarova Dilnoza and Salih Tiryaki's 2025 study argues that feelings of helplessness, powerlessness, and systemic foundations contributed to this phenomenon. Often, structural causes such as poverty, domestic violence, and limited legal protection for women were hidden under cultural customs. Analyzing the collected data, the authors of the study emphasize the persistence of gender stereotypes and fragile awareness of women's rights, which led to the consequences of self-immolation.

Gambling in post-Soviet Uzbekistan represented social instability and the changing moral norms of the remnants of Soviet gambling. Haworth (2008) argues in his research that gambling had its place in society because of the new capitalist order in which Uzbek men, in order to avoid responsibility, reflected a desire for risk. Beristenov (2023) examines gambling through the lens of sociology and community, emphasizing the underlying social factors and conditions above that encourage individual and group participation in gambling. Poverty and unemployment, weak social cohesion, and poor quality of life were central factors not only in the USSR but also in post-Soviet Uzbekistan, which left gambling as a collective and widespread "hobby" rather than an individual solution. Beristenov's findings show that in post-Soviet society, gambling functions as a method of social survival, where men usually relied on winning large amounts of money, but often did not get what they needed. The government, however, often overlooked these issues, preferring to tarnish these times, which did not help fix the problem.

In all these areas - labor, gender, and leisure - there is a common pattern: structural changes without corresponding social transformations. The legacy of Soviet collectivism, combined with traditional norms and state control, continues to shape behavior and justify systemic inequality. Researchers such as Bhat (2011), Alimova and Asimova (2000), Crowley (2016), Umarova and Tiryaki (2025) demonstrate how deeply rooted ideologies influence both work and gender roles, while culture and communication, according to these researchers, reinforce subordination to the authorities. All studies show that Uzbekistan is a society in transition, where the old way of life is combined with the new, power and freedom. People move through events that have been shaped by history and hierarchy, whether it's cotton fields, domestic suffering, or gambling halls. Understanding these interconnected systems requires more than just changes in economics or politics - it requires rethinking identity, values, and self-esteem in post-Soviet Uzbekistan. All studies concern social problems of the late Soviet period, suggesting several reasons for each issue, such as poverty, cultural norms and low living conditions. This research aims to consider these challenges together, mirroring their impact on Uzbek folk's lives.

Methodology

This study applies a descriptive historical approach to analyze the situation in Uzbekistan between 1980-1990 years. It involves various secondary sources, such as academic books, journal articles, and historical research that discusses Soviet Central Asia, child exploitation, gender inequality, and underground economies. These sources were reviewed to discover how social problems were connected to broader economic and political alternations in the Soviet Union. The research was carried by historical reports on the cotton case, which manifested in the widespread child labour. Key works by Alimova Dilarom and Nodira Azimova monitored how the status of Uzbek women shifted under Soviet rule. However, as official data on sensitive issues such as banned gambling and domestic violence were often unavailable, the paper focuses on the interpretations of scholars, sociologists, and anthropologists who have studied these problems in detail.

Results

Child Labour

In the 1980s-1990s, a great amount of Uzbek cotton was collected by ordinary people, often by children. Local governments and school administrators sent mostly the seventh grade students aged 13-14, and rarely the fifth grade students aged 11-12 to the fields of cotton to pick it up. Children were forced to go on cotton labour by the end of September, when schools were also closed for a period of cotton harvesting. Each student was controlled by headmasters who reported the amount of time he spent and the amount of cotton he gathered. Those who failed to meet their targets, or who picked a low quality crop, were punished, and their grades were lowered. Students who ran away from the cotton fields, or who refused to join, could get eviction.

The work included gathering cotton bushes, ploughing, planting, weeding, and hoeing. Even though it was written in law that children should not work for longer hours, in reality, the majority expressed that they worked up to 12 hours a day. It is still unclear about the payment of the labour, but each student could get 1200-1600 soms per day. It is the fact that child labour was cheap and certainly profitable (Bhat, 2011).

The conditions of the fields were awful. Students must have been under the sun for a long time, completing the hard work that was not suitable for mental and physical capabilities. Younger ones could leave home after work (but often they were free after 9 p.m.), but the older teenagers lived in dormitories, or even in farms. They did not have appropriate hygiene, fulfilling diet and necessary treatment. Consequently, children's health and well-being were affected negatively. Most of them became weak and more vulnerable to infections, and some of them even had chronic pain in body parts. Since students worked with pesticides, there was a high risk of health problems (for example, at too much exposure to pesticides, it might lead to cancer (Cavalier H., Trasande L., Porta M, 2023). They could not have treatment even at home, because the large percentage of families at that time was poor.

The forced labour also deprived them of the opportunity to get proper education. As the cotton period could take from two months till six months, children studied only partly, not fully learning the subjects. The survey (Bhat Bilal Ahmad, 2011) shows a net loss of about 25% of students' exposure to education. This difficult period caused developmental delays, taking away children's chance to implement good careers.

Women Self-Immolation

From the beginning of life, Uzbek traditions involved women marrying early (at 17-20 years). In harsh Soviet times, since most Uzbek families were unable to feed all members, marrying off a daughter was a kind of act of giving away the responsibility to another family. As scholars Alimova and Azimova (2000), the bride usually moved in with her husband's family where she occupied the lowest status. They were told to be modest, well-mannered and quiet; the education of the girl was ranked the lowest. The poor

treatment in marriage was a frequent phenomenon in Uzbekistan. It has been reported that when a young woman was unacceptable to her husband and his family after she was married, or if she was unable to have children, she was repeatedly criticized and ashamed in the community. Spousal abuse was common, but was considered a personal matter rather than a criminal act, so there are few recordings of this important issue. Additionally, women had no status in the community because the rural areas were governed by mahallas where only men were the part of them. The mahalla made decisions and enforced the laws. In turn, women found little justice among the society of men (Campbell, 2005).

Another key factor was the crushing poverty detailed in the accounts collected by Campbell (2005). Most of the women who attempted suicide lived in the villages (kishlocks). There was little employment available, and, consequently, people were poor. Electricity was only available for short periods of time during each day, or sometimes people lived without electricity for a whole day. Women must have cooked for big families with few products, so often they were left with no food.

Subsequently, young women, desperate to abuse, arranged marriages and poverty, pour gasoline or kerosene on themselves and set themselves on fire. It was more an act of desperation rather than an act of protest (Campbell, 2005). The self-immolation was often done in the presence of others to make the people abusing them feel the guilt. The fire was chosen as the most available method at that time; kerosene was spread around Uzbekistan, because during 80s, Uzbekistan was the third-largest producer of natural gas in the Soviet Union. Unfortunately, when a woman died after self-inflicted burns, her family could claim that the death was accidental in order to maintain family honor. Even if a woman had survived, she could claim that it was an accident. That is why, as Umarova and Tiryaki (2025) explain in their analysis of media coverage, it is still unknown how many women died as the result of self-immolation in Soviet time, but predicted to be as around 300. The act of self-immolation among young women could be more than expected.

Underground Gambling

In Soviet law, in the period of the new economic policy, all kinds of gambling were banned, but they were not seriously combated, and gambling business continued to exist illegally. At the beginning, the underground gambling got its popularity in the region of Russia, and then gradually scattered around the Soviet Union regions; Uzbekistan was not the exception. The gambling quickly occupied the territory of Uzbekistan, making men addicted to it (Haworth, 2008).

With the Soviet Union decline, the problem of decrease in morale and increase in crime and offences had a special place. As the level of poverty rose, men spent their time avoiding the realities of their lives. Thus, many men drank and, eventually, came to the solution of a harsh period in life - gambling. Along with alcoholism and drug addiction, gambling showed its impact (Beristenov, 2023).

The main part of gambling games was cards. In the game, everyone bet something valuable (mostly a large amount of money), and in the cards, the one who collected a huge number of points took away everything that was wagered from the rest. At first, it was just games of chance, but then the stakes increased, and simple cards became a symbol of the loss of not only value but also life. The stakes in the game grew larger and larger, and eventually, starting with money, men began to bet their houses, and sometimes even their wives. Since cards were a game of risk, men very often lost, enjoying this risk. As a result, the loss of property, home, and even a wife led men to suicide, as they could not cope with the fact of the loss. Along with gambling, so-called "mafia" groups were formed (Beristenov, 2023). These groups could have built their own system of underground gambling. They often beat them en masse, extorted money, and rarely even killed those who contradicted them or did not follow their instructions.

Since information on this topic was often ignored or concealed in Soviet times, the exact number of people affected by gambling is unknown. As was the case with self-immolations by women, talking about the loss of money and property at that time was considered a disgrace, so it was not made public. However, what is known is that the loss from simple card games was enormous for men and their families.

Discussion

The findings of this study exhibit how different social problems in late-1980s and 1990s Uzbekistan (child cotton labour, women's self-immolation, and underground gambling) were not separate occasions, but deeply connected with the economic crisis and cultural expectations of the period.

Child exploitation in cotton labour was at first considered as dedication to homeland and help to the nation. However, the reality was much worse. Students had to leave their studies in order to go to the fields of cotton. Working under the sun and among fertilizers more than half of a day, most of the children had physical and psychological problems since this kind of work was not suitable for children's capacity. Only between 2009 and 2012, the Uzbek government began to restrict the use of young children (Jurewicz, 2014). Eventually, under the international pressure, such as ILO and Human Rights Watch, the child labour was officially banned in 2013-2014.

Women's self-immolation, in contrast, exposed the convergence of tradition and despair. Firstly expected to be a sign of protest, the self-immolation actually was only desperation that women could not stand. They did not aim to raise insurrection, they only saw suicide as the solution of all family issues and abusive relationships. Since fire has always had a meaning in almost all cultures, the choice of fire for suicide was mistaken to have a symbolism. In fact, interviews from survivors that Campbell (2005) took reported that fire was the most available method and kerosene was in widespread use. To combat this problem, Dr. Bibisora Oripova set a goal to provide care for women who self-immolate. Finally, in 1999-2000 she developed the Umid Center in Samarkand, a shelter specialised for survivors. The shelter helps women and their children who have experienced domestic violence, provides them with psychological, medical and legal support, as well as helps in professional retraining and acquiring new knowledge.

Underground gambling among men represented another dimension of social tension. In the context of the collapse of the economy, gambling was both a risky alternative source of income and a form of escape from reality (Haworth, 2008). Its devastating effects often deprived men of their means of money and their own homes. It was only in 2006 that this situation worsened, and in 2007 Uzbekistan passed a law banning gambling. This has certainly helped with huge losses, but so far gambling has not completely disappeared from both Uzbekistan and the world, but has transformed into less dangerous games, such as online betting companies.

Taken together, these problems demonstrate a society caught between the official Soviet ideals of progress and the harsh realities of economic poverty, gender inequality, and social disillusionment. Each issue highlights the overall failure of late Soviet social policy to protect its most vulnerable members.

Conclusion

In Uzbekistan, child cotton labour, women's self-immolation, and underground gambling were all interconnected to the economic and social structures of the Soviet and post-Soviet periods. The social problems of the late 1980s and 1990s were not isolated but rather mirrored larger structural shortcomings, as the Soviet system entered a crash. Reviewing historical documentaries, now it becomes clear that social peace cannot be achieved only through economic growth but requires systems that value human dignity, equality, and the protection of rights of all people.

Child labor in the cotton fields has shown that production goals are set higher than the well-being of children, and it is necessary to sacrifice their development, education, health and general well-being in order to profit from the sale of cotton. The self-immolation of women revealed the enormous consequences of gender inequality and the lack of support and protection for women from domestic violence, which left little chance for the proper administration of justice. At the same time, underground gambling demonstrated the ways in which men sought to earn money and escape from the reality of the economic crisis, often to the detriment of wealth and family stability.

References

- Alimova, D., & Azimova, N. (2000). Women's position in Uzbekistan before and after independence. In F. Acar & A. Güneş-Ayata (Eds.), *Gender and identity construction: Women of Central Asia, the Caucasus and Turkey* (pp. 293–304). Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004492028_016
- Beristenov, S. O. (2023). Social causes and preconditions of community involvement in gambling. *The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology*, 5(08), 14–18.
- Bhat, B. A. (2011). *Child labour in the cotton industry of Uzbekistan: A sociological study* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Kashmir).
- Campbell, E. A. (2005). *Perspectives on self-immolation experiences among Uzbek women* (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Tennessee).
- Crowley, K. (2016). Understanding Uzbek child rearing as a mediating factor in the government's reliance on child forced labor during the annual cotton harvest: A pilot project.
- Haworth, L. (2008). Russian roulette? Gambling in the post-Soviet era. *Gaming Law Review and Economics*, 12(5), 466–469. <https://doi.org/10.1089/gltre.2008.12502>
- Jurewicz, P. (2014). Reducing child labor in Uzbekistan: Lessons learned and next steps. *UC Davis Journal of International Law & Policy*, 21, 191.
- Umarova, D., & Tiryaki, S. (2025). Media coverage of female suicide during the transition period. *American Journal of Social Sciences and Humanity Research*, 5(05), 324–326.

